

THE CONCEPT OF TRAFFIC RULES AND SAFETY

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Abstract: The following article provides information about traffic rules and safety issues, how the concept of traffic rules and safety is important for everyone's life and by doing so, a person can help ensure the safety of himself and others.

Key words: safe, security, law, statistics, event

The concept of traffic rules and safety is important for everyone's life because this concept helps to ensure the safety of people. Traffic rules and safety issues are viewed with great attention in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Below are some of the reforms that have been implemented to ensure strict traffic and safety enforcement.

- **Laws on road safety:** There are laws on road safety in the Republic of Uzbekistan. These laws confirm traffic rules and other regulatory legal documents related to ensuring road safety.
- **Compliance with traffic rules:** Control over the compliance of road users with traffic rules is carried out. This includes compliance with the requirements of legislation on the organization of control and the organization of traffic.
- **Safety of vehicles:** Procedures and requirements for ensuring the safety of vehicles are established in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Vehicles must undergo a mandatory technical inspection, and drivers are required to comply with the work and rest hours established by law.
- **Traffic order:** In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the traffic order is determined and vehicles must drive on the right. Free and unhindered movement on the roads will be strengthened in accordance with the traffic rules.
- **Bulky and heavy loads:** In accordance with traffic rules, bulky and heavy loads should be transported in road transport in order to ensure traffic safety. This procedure is determined based on the total weight and dimensions of the vehicles.
- **Road safety statistics:** There are statistics about people killed or injured in road accidents. According to these data, road safety issues are still seen as problems that need to be solved.
- The information about updates on the basis of traffic safety statistics was provided by the General Directorate of Traffic Safety of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its regional offices.

According to statistics:

1. The number of traffic violations: during the 9 months of 2019, there were a total of 4 million in Uzbekistan. 607 thousand 34 traffic violations were detected. 2 million of this number. 55,254 gross violations, 25,120 drunk drivers, and 252,072 pedestrians were registered.

2. Types of violations: During this period, 19,436 cases of using a cell phone while driving a vehicle, 779,909 cases of driving a vehicle without wearing a seat belt, 628 cases of using or arbitrarily installing monitors, 41,179 vehicle insurance policy violations management violations were detected.

3. Offenses and punishments: administrative documents against 18,422 offenders were sent to judicial authorities for appropriate measures, and 8,492 (46.1 percent) were deprived of the right to drive a vehicle. Among them, formalized administrative documents against 12,778 drivers who drove vehicles under the influence of alcohol were sent to judicial authorities, 8,639 (67.6 percent) were deprived of the right to drive a vehicle, and 795 were sentenced to administrative imprisonment.

4. Number of accidents and injuries: The number of traffic accidents increased by 16.5% (from 6,236 to 5,207), the number of fatalities increased by 13.1% (from 1,607 to 1,396), and the number of injuries increased by 17.8% (from 5,864 from 4821 people) decreased. The number of traffic accidents involving children is 10.7% (876 out of 981), 18.4% of accidents caused by drivers' fault (4567 out of 5594), 32.6% of accidents caused by drunken drivers (from 135 to 91), traffic accidents involving pedestrians decreased by 23.6% (from 3332 to 2544).

These statistics will help to study the measures used in the field of road safety, and it will be possible to get information about the consequences of traffic violations.

Conclusion: The implementation of the collection of road safety statistics is important in defining measures and policies aimed at increasing road safety in Uzbekistan. This information helps to give a general idea about traffic rules and safety issues in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Road safety is an important issue and important for everyone's life.

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